

Questionnaire for the Staff of the Galician Public Library Network on Digital Reading and Electronic Lending Services.

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Qualtrics survey flow

Standard: Consent (1 Question)

Block: Sociodemographic data (3 Questions)

Standard: Job performance (5 Questions)

Standard: Attitudes towards digital reading (11 Questions)

Standard: Attitudes towards the electronic loan service and level of knowledge (17 Questions)

Standard: Open Question (1 Question)

Beginning of the block: Consent

Q0.1

Your answers are anonymous and will be used exclusively for research purposes in compliance with current legislation*. Do you wish to continue?

** The data provided will be managed in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, as well as with Organic Law 3/2018 of 5 December on the Protection of Personal Data and the guarantee of digital rights.*

Yes

No

Skip to: End of survey Yes Your answers are anonymous and will be used exclusively for research and action purposes.... = No.

End of block: Consent

Beginning of the block: Sociodemographic data

Q1.1 Sex

Male

Female

Q1.2 Age

▼ Between 18 and 24 years old ... 65 and over

Q1.3 Level of education completed

- Middle School
- High School
- Advanced Technical Certificate
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- Ph.D.
- Other (please indicate which ones) _____

End of block: Sociodemographic data

Beginning of the block: Job performance

Q2.1 You work in a public library managed by:

- A municipal public authority
 - The Galician regional government (Xunta de Galicia)
 - Other ((please specify below) _____
-

Q2.2 In which province and municipality is the library where you work located?

Province

Municipality

Population range (pre-filled with INE 2021 data)

▼ Coruña, A ... Pontevedra ~ Vilanova de Arousa ~ 10.001-50.000

Q2.3 What is your position in the library?

- Library Assistant
- Librarian (A2)
- Librarian (A1)
- Library Manager
- Other (please specify) _____

Q2.4 What tasks do you usually perform in the library (You may select multiple tasks)?

- Lending, returns, renewals
 - Answering bibliographic queries
 - General attention to users (questions about library operations, searching for a title, etc.)
 - User registration
 - User training and guided tours
 - Cataloguing
 - Copy registration, labeling, etc.
 - Management of social media or the library website
 - Collection development (acquisitions, weeding, donations, etc.)
 - Organizing activities (book clubs, courses, workshops, etc.)
 - Library management (reports, budgets, staff, etc.)
 - Other (please specify below) _____
-

Q2.5 Do you consider GaliciaLe (the Galician Catalogue and eBiblio Galicia) in your work? For example, when informing users about this service during registration, selecting a book for your library collection, conducting a guided tour, or searching for a topic of interest to the user, etc.?

- Always
- Generally
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

End of block: Job performance

Beginning of the block: Attitudes towards digital reading

Q3.1 How often do you read books?

- Every day or almost every day
- Once or twice a week
- At least once a month
- At least once a quarter
- Rarely
- Never

Skip to Q3.5 Yes. How often do you read books? = Never.

Q3.2 On average, how many books do you read per year?

▼ None ... More than 20

Q3.3 How often do you read e-books?

- Every day or almost every day
- Once or twice a week
- At least once a month
- At least once a quarter
- Rarely
- Never

Jump to: Q3.5 Yes. How often do you read books in electronic format? = Never

Show this question:

If How often do you read books in electronic format? != Never

Q3.4 On average, how many of the books you read per year are in digital format?

▼ None ... More than 20

Q3.5 Which reading format do you feel most comfortable with?

- Print
 - Digital
 - Both
-

Show this question:

Which reading format do you feel most comfortable with? = Paper

Or Which reading format do you feel more comfortable with? = Both

Q3.6 You prefer print books because.... (You may select more than one reason)

- They are more convenient for underlining, annotating, etc.
 - Unlike screens, they do not cause eyestrain
 - You retain information more easily
 - You can leaf through the book, touch it, etc.
 - Other reasons (please specify below)
-

Show this question:

If Which reading format do you feel most comfortable with? = Electronic

Or Which reading format do you feel more comfortable with? = Both

Q3.7 You prefer e-books because.... (You may select more than one reason)

- They are more convenient for underlining, annotating, etc.
 - They are available anytime, anywhere (mobile, tablet, etc.).
 - They allow you to browse, play multimedia content, etc., while reading
 - They offer greater economic savings
 - Other reasons (please specify below)
-

Show this question:

If How often do you read books in electronic format? != Never

And How often do you read books? != Never

Q3.8 On which device(s) do you read e-books most frequently (You may select more than one option)?

- E-reader (electronic book reader)
 - Mobile phone
 - Tablet
 - Desktop computer/laptop
 - Other (please specify below) _____
-

Show this question:

If How often do you read e-books? != Never

And How often do you read books? != Never

Q3.9 To access e-books, you generally use:

- Electronic lending services such as GaliciaLe (the Galician Catalogue or eBiblio Galicia).
 - Subscription-based services such as 24symbols, Nextory, Amazon Kindle Unlimited, etc.
 - Online e-bookstores such as Fnac, La Casa del Libro, Amazon, etc.
 - Other means (please specify) _____
-

Q3.10 Indicate which of these services best fits each of the following statements (you may select more than one service):

	E-book lending services (eBiblio, etc.)	E-book subscription services (24symbols, Nextory, etc.)	Online e-bookstores (Amazon, Fnac, Casa del Libro, etc.)	Do not know /No answer
There is a greater variety of titles and topics.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It accommodates more small and independent publishers.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It is more affordable.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Books are more widely available for reading.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It is easier to use.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The deadlines for reading a book better fit my needs.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It preserves my privacy more adequately.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q3.11 Please rate your level of agreement or disagreement with the following statements about digital reading:

	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Digital reading will progressively replace print reading.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Print reading will last longer than expected.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In addition to encouraging print reading, public libraries should promote digital reading.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Public libraries currently play an important role in promoting digital reading.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of block: Attitudes towards digital reading

Beginning of the block: Attitudes towards the electronic lending service and level of awareness

Q4.1 Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue) to access any of the formats it offers, such as magazines, books, films, or audiobooks?

- Yes
- No
- Occasionally

Jump to: Q4.10 If Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue... = No

Show this question:

If Do you use the digital loan service GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the GalicianCatalogue,... != No

Q4.2 Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue) to read books?

- Yes
- No
- Occasionally

Jump to: Q4.10 If Do you use the GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue...)? = No.

Show this question:

If Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue)? != No

Q4.3 For reading books, which do you use most frequently

- eBiblio Galicia
- The Galician Catalogue
- Both

Show this question:

If Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue)? != No

Q4.4 The last e-book you read from GaliciaLe was from:

- eBiblio Galicia
- The Galician Catalogue

Show this question:

If Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue)... != No

Q4.5 To access eBiblio Galicia e-books, you usually read them using...(You may select more than one option):

- Streaming
- Software for reading on a desktop or e-reader
- The eBiblio app
- The Adobe Digital Editions app
- Other apps or software (please specify) _____
- I do not read books from eBiblio Galicia.

Show this question:

If Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue)... != No

Q4.6 Which device(s) do you use most frequently to read eBiblio Galicia e-books? (You may select more than one option.)

- E-reader
 - Mobile phone
 - Tablet
 - Desktop computer/laptop
 - Other (please specify) _____
 - I do not read books from eBiblio Galicia.
-

Show this question:

If you use the digital loan service GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue), do you... != No

Q4.7 To access e-books from the Galician Catalogue, you usually read them using... (You may select more than one option):

- Streaming
- Software for reading on a desktop or e-reader
- The Adobe Digital Editions app
- Other apps or software (please specify) _____
- I do not read e-books from the Galician Catalogue.

Show this question:

If Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue),.. != No

Q4.8 Which device(s) do you use most frequently to read e-books from the Galician Catalogue? (You may select more than one option.)

- E-reader
- Mobile phone
- Tablet
- Desktop computer/laptop
- Other (please specify) _____
- I do not read e-books from the Galician Catalogue.

Show this question:

If Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue)? != No

Q4.9 From your experience as a user, rate your level of agreement or disagreement with the following statements about GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue):

	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
I can easily find information (help pages, frequently asked questions, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I almost always find titles and topics I am interested in.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The titles I am interested in are usually available (I can borrow them immediately).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is a convenient service (accessible at any time and from any place).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I need help managing two environments (the Galician Catalogue and eBiblio Galicia).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I need help with the apps.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I need help with the lending and early return processes.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I need help using this service on my devices.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I need help with downloading e-books.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Since the COVID-19 pandemic, I am more interested in this service.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Show this question:

If Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue)? = No

Or Do you use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue)? = No

Q4.10 Why do you not use GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue) to read e-books? (You may select more than one reason).

- I need help reading GaliciaLe e-books (e.g., with the loan process, downloading, managing apps, etc.)
 - I cannot find the titles, topics, etc. I am interested in
 - The titles I am interested in are usually checked out
 - I do not use it to read e-books, but I do use it to listen to audiobooks
 - I do not use it to read e-books, but I do use it to watch movies
 - I do not use it to read e-books, but I do use it to read magazines
 - I do not read e-books
 - I do not read books
 - Other reasons (please specify) _____
-

Q4.11 Based on your experience with users, rate the degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements about GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue):

	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Do not know/No answer
Users can easily find information (help pages, frequently asked questions, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Users almost always find titles and topics they are interested in.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Titles that interest users are usually available (they do not have to place a hold or wait to borrow them).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is a convenient service for users (accessible at any time and from any place).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Users need help managing two environments (the Galician Catalogue and eBiblio Galicia).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Users need help with the apps.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Users need help with the lending and early return processes.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Users need help with using this service on their devices.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Users need help downloading e-books.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Since the COVID-19 pandemic, users have been more interested in this service.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q4.12 Rate which platform (eBiblio Galicia or the Galician Catalogue) best fits the following statements:

	Both equally	eBiblio Galicia	The Galician Catalogue	Neither	Do not know/No answer
Information is displayed more clearly (reading options, availability of books and formats, aids, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The interface is more user-friendly.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The user session offers more functionalities, information, etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The lending and early return processes are easier.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The download process for e-books is easier.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reading adapts better to all devices.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The content is more attractive.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Titles are more frequently available (no need to place a hold or wait to borrow them).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Most users are more interested in using...	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Since the COVID-19 pandemic, users have shown more interest in...	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The incidents reported to us by users are more frequent.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I receive more queries about...	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q4.13 Rate the degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements about GaliciaLe (eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue) and your library:

	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
It is an additional service that my library should offer.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is necessary for my library to promote this service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is necessary for my library to train users on how to use this service.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This service complements my library's collection.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This service threatens the survival of in-person services offered by my library.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q4.14 Please answer "Yes" or "No" to the following questions:

	No	Yes
I know what DRM is and what it is used for.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I know the difference between concurrent use and concurrent license.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I know how many devices can be linked with Adobe Digital Editions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Besides eBiblio and Adobe Digital Editions app, I am aware of other reading applications.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I know what the ePub format is.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I know the difference between an e-reader and an e-book.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I know how to transfer an e-book from a desktop to an e-reader.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am familiar with the different license acquisition models available on the market.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q4.15 Rate the degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements:

	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
I can assist users who have difficulties with the electronic lending service.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I need ongoing training to effectively answer users' questions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I spend a significant amount of time explaining how the electronic lending service works and helping users resolve issues and questions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q4.16 Rate the effectiveness of the following actions to promote digital reading and electronic lending (1 being the least effective and 5 being the most effective):

	1	2	3	4	5
Training borrowers on using devices, reading applications, the lending process, etc.	<input type="radio"/>				
Institutional promotional campaigns targeting all users of the Library Network.	<input type="radio"/>				
Institutional promotional campaigns aimed at the general public.	<input type="radio"/>				
Promotion by library staff (e.g. informing new users about this service, offering an e-book as an alternative when a print book is not available, using the library's social media, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>				
Ongoing education and training for public library workers.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q4.17 When a user comes to you with an issue related to the e-lending service that you do not know how to resolve, most of the time you: (You can select more than one option)

- Search for information on the help pages of eBiblio Galicia and the Galician Catalogue.
 - Ask a colleague for help.
 - Submitting a support request to the User Service Center (CAU).
 - Contact the Library Service directly.
 - Inform users that you are unable help them.
 - Search for information on the Internet.
 - Other (please indicate what other means you use).
-

End of block: Attitudes towards the electronic lending service and level of awareness

Beginning of block: Open-ended question

Q5.1 Below, you can make any comments you consider relevant about GaliciaLe (the Galician Catalogue and eBiblio Galicia) or digital reading:

End of block: Open question